

Further Studies on Sylvone : A Lignan Constituent of *Piper sylvaticum* Roxb.

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Further nmr studies on sylvone, a novel lignan constituent of *Piper sylvaticum*, were carried out to clarify stereochemical features, to establish the structure and stereochemistry of borohydride reduction products and for complete nmr signal assignment of sylvone and derivatives.

The chemical investigation of *Piper sylvaticum* Roxb. led to the isolation of several lignan and amide constituents¹. The structure elucidation of a novel 2,3,4-trisubstituted furanoid lignan, sylvone, has been reported earlier by us². It was decided to investigate the nmr characteristics of sylvone and its derivatives in order to obtain more information about chemical shifts and coupling patterns and also to clarify those stereochemical features which had remained obscured earlier. Our earlier communication had reported the formation of two amorphous products when sylvone was subjected to borohydride reduction. One of them was identified as a dihydrosylvone, without total stereochemical identification. The structure elucidation of the second product and the stereochemistry of both borohydride reduction products have been achieved. Detailed 300 MHz ¹H- and 75.5 MHz ¹³C-nmr analysis as well as two-dimensional nmr experiments (cosy, heteronuclear-shift correlations) were performed.

Results and Discussion

Sylvone was assigned the structure and relative stereochemistry (1)² from chemical transformations and spectroscopical studies of sylvone and the transformation products particularly by high-field one-dimensional nmr studies.

The complete 300 MHz ¹H-nmr assignments of sylvone are collected in Table 1. The estimation of the exact coupling constants and chemical shifts were done by computer-aided spectrum simulation by the PANIC programme (Parameter Adjustment in Nmr by Iteration Calculation) available in Bruker software. It would not have been possible to determine all the chemical shifts and coupling constants without this analysis. $J_{3,4}$ was found to be 2.9 Hz, thus confirming the *trans*-disposition of H-3 and H-4 (dihedral angle of $\sim 105-110^\circ$ in Dreiding model). H-4 nearly bisected the projected angle between H_A-5 and H_B-5 so that the $J_{4,5A}$ and $J_{4,5B}$ have almost similar magnitudes. The relative stereochemistry of sylvone as represented earlier², was thus conclusively established. The systematic nomenclature of sylvone would be 2*R*'-(3',4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-3*R*'-(hydroxymethyl), 4*S*'-(3'',4'',5''-trimethoxybenzoyl)tetrahydrofuran.

A two-dimensional heteronuclear-shift correlation experiment of sylvone was done by the XHCORR sequence³. The delay parameters were optimised for long-range couplings to emphasise cross-peaks due to $^3J_{CH}$ and $^2J_{CH}$ in the 2D-spectrum (Fig. 1). Thus complete ¹³C-signal assignments were achieved (Table 2)—all the methoxyl groups and the oxygenated carbons could be precisely assigned. Further, certain assignments made in our previous paper² had to be revised (Table 1).

Sodium borohydride reduction of sylvone in methanol gave two amorphous products, separated by ptlc, the major component of which was characterised earlier as dihydrosylvone², though the stereochemistry at the new chiral centre remained undefined. It has now been possible to identify

TABLE 1—300 MHz ¹H NMR ASSIGNMENTS OF 1-3 IN CDCl₃

Proton no.	Compound 1			Compound 2			Compound 3						
	Chemical shift (δ)	Multi- plicity	J Hz	All corre- lations from COSY-IR	Chemical shift (δ)	Multi- plicity	J Hz	All corre- lations from COSY-IR	Chemical shift (δ)	Multi- plicity	J Hz	Decoupling information to Change On irradiation of	
H-2	4.82	d	6.0	H-2', H-6'	4.86	d	7.1	H-3, H-2', H-6'	4.97	d	8.1	s	H-3 and 4
H-3	2.67	m	6.5, 6.0, 2.9	H-2, H-3 ^a , H-4	2.30	m	4.0, 6.3, 6.5, 7.1	H-2, H-4	2.4-2.6 ^a	m	—	—	—
HA-3 ^a]	3.20	d	6.5	H-3	3.15	dd	6.5, 11.2	HB-3 ^a	3.25 ^b	dd	4.0, 10.6	br s	HB-3 ^a
HB-3 ^a]	4.09	m	7.7, 5.6, 2.9	HA-5, HB-5	3.00	dd	6.3, 11.2	HA-3 ^a	3.02 ^b	dist t	10.0, 10.6	—	—
H-4	—	—	—	—	2.56	m	4.0, 7.0, 8.4	H-3, H-4 ^a , HA, HB-5	2.4-2.6 ^a	m	—	—	—
H-4 ^a	—	—	—	—	4.66	d	7.0	H-4	4.37	d	9.1	s	H-3 and 4
HA-5	4.21	dist t	7.7, 8.1	H-4, HB-5	4.21	dist t	8.4, 8.4	HB-5	observed	—	—	—	—
HB-5	4.02	dist dd	5.6, 8.1	H-4, HA-5	3.80	dist t	8.4, 8.4	HA-5	3.36	dist t	8.6	d	H-3 and 4
OCH ₃]	3.71	s	—	H-2', H-5'	3.80	s	—	H-2', H-5'	3.80	s	—	—	—
OH]	3.70	s	—	H-6'	3.79	s	—	H-6'	3.79	s	—	—	—
H-2']	3.65	s	—	H-2', 6''	3.78	s	—	H-2', 6''	3.78	s	—	—	—
H-5']	1.50	br s	—	—	1.50	br s	—	—	1.50	br s	—	—	—
H-6']	6.61	s	—	OCH ₃	6.74	s	—	OCH ₃	6.70-6.76	m	—	—	—
H-2', 6'']	7.20	s	—	OCH ₃	6.53	s	—	OCH ₃	6.52	s	—	—	—

Chemical shifts and coupling constants are accurate to within ±0.2-0.3 Hz, comparable to Hz/pt. in experimental spectra, calculated by PANIC analysis. ^aH-3 and H-4 showed overlapped signals. ^bIrradiation of H-3 and H-4 caused the H-3^a system to simplify to an AB system.

 Fig. 1. 300 MHz ^1H -75.5 MHz ^{13}C -nmr heteronuclear shift correlation spectrum of **1** in CDCl_3 , using the XHCORR sequence optimised for long range coupling.

 TABLE 2—75.5 MHz ^{13}C NMR ASSIGNMENTS OF **1-3** IN CDCl_3

Carbon no.	Compound 1			2	3
	Chemical shifts (δ)	Correlations of carbon signals with protons observed in XHCORR-I.R spectrum	Chemical shifts (δ)		
2	81.50	H-2 1J , H-2' 2J , H-6' 2J	82.12	82.84	
3	49.74	—	49.59	49.86	
3 α	62.02	—	62.86	63.83	
4	48.86	—	47.67	52.79	
4 α	198.46	H-2'', 6'' 2J	75.67	77.23	
5	69.16	—	69.92	70.36	
1'	130.62	H-5' 1J	131.42	131.42	
2'	109.09	—	109.49	109.75 ^a	
3'	149.13	H-5' 2J , OCH ₃ (3') 2J	149.19	149.19	
4'	148.42	H-2' 2J , H-6' 2J , OCH ₃ (4') 1J	148.53	148.53	
5'	111.36	—	111.42	110.05 ^a	
6'	117.83	H-6' 1J , H-2' 2J	118.23	118.54	
1''	131.40	H-2'', 6'' 2J	138.41	138.41	
2'', 6''	106.50	H-2'', 6'' 1J	103.87	103.61	
3'', 5''	153.18	H-2'', 6'' 2J , OCH ₃ (3'', 5'') 2J	153.45	153.45	
4''	143.10	H-2'', 6'' 2J , OCH ₃ (4'') 2J	137.84	137.84	
3', 4'-OCH ₃	55.93	OCH ₃ (3', 4') 1J	55.99	55.99	
3'', 5''-OCH ₃	56.34	OCH ₃ (3'', 5'') 1J	56.31	56.31	
4''-OCH ₃	60.88	OCH ₃ (4'') 1J	60.82	60.82	

^aInterchangeable.

the second product also as a dihydrosylvone, diastereoisomeric with the earlier one. The structures and stereochemistry of both were settled from spectroscopical studies. The previously identi-

fied compound was designated dihydrosylvone-A (2*R**, 3*R**, 4*S**, 4 α *S**) (**2**) while the other was designated dihydrosylvone-B (2*R**, 3*R**, 4*S**, 4 α *R**) (**3**).

Fig. 2. 300 MHz ^1H - ^1H COSY (LR) -90° spectrum of dihydroxylvone (A) (2) in CDCl_3 .

The ^1H - ^1H COSY (long-range) (Fig. 2) of dihydroxylvone-A was recorded in addition to selective decoupling experiments, for complete signal assignments (Table 1). The exact chemical shifts and coupling constants were determined by the use of the PANIC programme (Table 1). ^{13}C -nmr assignments of dihydroxylvone-A (2) are given in Table 2. The most marked changes were observed with the carbons C-4, C-4 α , C-1'', C-2'', C-6'' and C-4'' as would be expected on reduction of the 4 α -carbonyl group.

Dihydroxylvone-B (3) had the molecular formula $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_8$, as 2. Its ir spectrum resembled that of 2, showing a broad hydroxyl band ($3000-3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$). Its mass spectrum did not exhibit a M^+ peak and instead showed a $M-18$ ($M-\text{H}_2\text{O}$) peak. The $75.5\text{ MHz }^{13}\text{C}$ -nmr of 3 (Table 2) was remarkably similar to that of 2 with most of the peaks only slightly shifted. The most significant change was the down-field shift of C-4 from $\delta 47.67$ to 52.79 , thus predicting a change in configuration at the chiral centre C-4 α . Its $300\text{ MHz }^1\text{H}$ -nmr spectrum showed the same number of protons as 2; the differing chemical shifts and coupling constants indicated stereochemical and

Fig. 3.

conformational differences. Complete assignments are collected in Table 1.

The relative configuration of the dihydroxylvone-A and -B were settled as 2 and 3 respectively, from ^1H -nmr data. The possible conformation about the H bond for both compounds are given in Fig. 3. Consideration of non-bonded steric

